

Research Article**Assessment of the Mechanization of Cassava Processing in Kwara State, Nigeria**

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Abstract

This study was conducted in Kwara State Nigeria, to assess the level of mechanization of cassava processing. Data was collected using multi-stage sampling technique randomly selecting one hundred and twenty (120) processing centres from two ADP agricultural zones in Kwara State. A structured interview schedule was used as an instrument to elicit information on types and number of processing machines available to processors, gender of operators, source of power and type of prime mover, mode of operation and constraints to mechanization of cassava processing. The data collected was analyzed using simple descriptive statistics like mean, percentages and cross tabulations. Chi-square (X^2) analysis was used to test the independence of machine operators against sex (gender). The major constraints to mechanization of cassava processing were identified, rated on a 4 points Likert-Type scale and ranked to determine their severity. The results showed that the level of mechanization of cassava processing in Kwara State is generally low, with the most commonly available processing equipment as the peeling tool (common knife), the grater and local frying pans. Over 70% of the processing equipment are manually operated, while electricity accounted for only about 0.5%. The chi-square test for the processing equipment versus the sex of the operator revealed that gender (sex) is dependent on processing machine at 1% level of significance. The 'very severe' constraints to mechanization of cassava processing are lack of credit, scarcity of spare parts and lack of electricity, while Poor quality of fabrication materials and Inappropriate processing equipment are considered 'Not severe'. The study recommended appropriate government policies aimed at reducing interest rates, encouraging research and development and provision of massive rural infrastructures.

Key words: Mechanization, Cassava processing, Processing equipment, Constraints

Introduction

The importance of cassava in food security and income generation can never be over emphasized. As a rural food staple and cash crop for urban consumption, cassava is an essential part of the diet of more than 70 million Nigerians (FAO 2012). Cassava's starchy roots produce more food energy per unit of land than any other staple crop. The amount of carbohydrates contained in dry cassava roots is higher than maize or any other cereal. Except possibly for sugar cane, the cassava plant gives the highest yield of food energy per cultivated area among crop plants. It supplies close to 40 percent of calorific requirement of Nigerians (O'Hair 2009). Cassava does not only play prominent role as rural staple food and cash crop for urban consumption, but provides raw materials for industries (starch, textiles, fuel, confectionery just to mention a few), as well as foreign exchange earner (Dixon *et al.*, 2009).

Nigeria's cassava production, which presently stands at over 40 million metric tons (MT) per annum, is by far the largest in the world; a third more than the production in Brazil and almost double the production of Indonesia and Thailand (IFPRI, 2010). This is about 20 percent of the global market share (FAO, 2011). From projections based on various cassava initiatives, Nigeria's cassava production is expected to double by year 2020, thus helping to sustain Africa's leadership in cultivating 62 percent of total world production (ECP, 2010). Nigeria is however not among the top 10 exporters of cassava worldwide and exported just about 0.55 million tonnes of its fresh/dried cassava in 2011 (Tijaja, 2010). In contrast to Thailand, where cassava processing is highly mechanized, and majority is exported to China and Europe as dried chips for animal feed, the larger proportion of the cassava produced in Nigeria is used for human consumption. This is in agreement with (Adeoti and Adeoti 2010; Dada *et al.*, 2010) who reported that due to the low level of mechanization of cassava processing and traditional method of processing, about 80 percent of the cassava produced in Nigeria is consumed in the form of human food with less quantity being used for animal feed and industrial purposes.

Cassava roots are bulky with about 70% moisture content, and therefore transportation becomes difficult and expensive. The roots and leaves contain varying amounts of cyanogenic glycosides (HCN) which is toxic to humans and animals. Therefore, cassava must be processed into various forms in order to increase the shelf life of the products, facilitate transportation and marketing, reduce cyanide content and improve palatability (IFPRI, 2010). Essentially, cassava processing are those agro-industrial activities which are related to the transformation of the root crop with a view to modifying its physical, chemical and rheological characteristics thereby enhancing its value (Olomo, 2006). The purposes of cassava processing are to facilitate the transportability of processed products,

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reduce perishability, reduce toxicity, enhance edibility and nutritive quality, adapt to alternative uses, stabilize the product for storage and guarantee higher prices for farmers through price stability.

Mechanization of cassava processing refers to the process whereby equipment, machineries and implements are utilized in changing cassava roots to various forms, products and recipes to boost agricultural and food production. In mechanization of cassava processing, agricultural machineries, machines, equipment and tools are applied in carrying out unit operations in the day-to-day activities of processing cassava in order to increase output and quality of cassava products (Folaranmi, 2011). Mechanized cassava processing utilizes equipment and machines in processing operations related to washing, cleaning, sorting, peeling, grating, pulverizing, cutting, slicing, dicing and chipping. It also involves drying, sieving (sifting), grading and packaging. Up till now, most of these operations are still being done manually, and they are generally labour intensive, arduous in nature, time consuming and unsuitable for large scale production (Adetan *et al.*, 2003; Quaye *et al.*, 2009), due to their low output capacity among other negative attributes. According to Achem (2011), mechanization of cassava processing operations will no doubt play a pivotal role in removing the negative attributes of the traditional processing techniques and promote timely large scale processing of the tubers in hygienic environment. The continued increase in output has raised the need for improved cassava processing technologies to absorb the increases, produce diversified and high quality cassava products suitable for industrial use and export. Mechanized processing will increase post-harvest management of cassava crop output and guarantee effective preservation and utilization of cassava for food security.

The recent transformation of cassava from a low profile into an industrial raw material, coupled with the new cassava revolutionary policies of the Federal Government of Nigeria have resulted in a serious surge in the demand for cassava and cassava-based products locally and the world over. However, cassava processors are currently finding it extremely difficult to respond positively to this increase in demand due to the prevalence of the traditional processing methods employed in the processing operations. Davies *et al* (2008) undertook a survey of cassava processing machinery and reported that grater, dewatering press, chipping machine, sifter and milling machines were available to cassava processors. Over 80 percent of the machines were diesel powered and operated by men. In 2010, Kolawole *et al.* (2010) examined the Nigeria experience of sustaining food security through improved cassava processing technology. They reported that the most adopted cassava processing technologies were the grater and dewatering press. However, appropriate and fully developed peeling technology has remained a great challenge to researchers and fabricators because of the irregularity in the shape of cassava

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tuber. The contribution of C:AVA (Cassava: Adding Value for Africa) project to income of processors was examined by Odunaya (2013). He concluded that project intervention in providing critical processing equipment led to changes in the volume of cassava processed, change in the processing cost and change in assets and expenditure of beneficiary processors. Similarly, the different methods being used by women cassava processors and the stages and time spent on each operation were identified and analyzed by Okorji *et al.* (2003). The study identified 3 cassava processing methods namely; traditional, modern and hybridized (trado-modern).

The main objective of this study is to assess the level mechanization of cassava processing in Kwara State. The specific objectives are to:

- (i) Identify the cassava processing equipment (number and types) available to processors in the State and the most prominently adopted ones;
- (ii) Determine the power source and mode of operating the cassava processing equipment/machines;
- (iii) Examine gender relationship in the operation of cassava processing machines;
- (iv) Investigate the constraints to mechanization of cassava processing in Kwara State.

Methodology

This study was conducted in Kwara State, Nigeria. The State has a land mass of about 32,500 square kilometers (Km²), and it is situated between the coordinates 6.50° and 11.50° North latitudes of the Equator and longitudes 2.80° and 7.50° East. The average temperature varies between 27°C to 35°C. The rainfall pattern follows a tropical type, with mean annual rainfall varying between 1000mm and 1500mm. The state is cohabited by four major ethnic groups including Yoruba, Nupe, Fulani and Baruba (KWSG Diary 2006). Kwara State has sixteen Local Government Areas (LGA's) with the capital and seat of government at Ilorin. To facilitate delivery of extension services, the LGAs are divided into four (4) agricultural zones with headquarters located at Kaiama (zone A), Pategi (zone B), Igbaja (zone C) and Malete (zone D).

A multi-stage sampling technique was adopted for this study. Two out of the four agricultural zones noted for cassava processing (Zones C and D) were first purposively selected. These two zones covered 12 out of the 16 LGAs in the state. In the second stage, three LGAs were randomly selected from each of the two zones. The third stage involved the random selection of 20 processing centres from each of the LGAs, making a total of 120 processing centres. A cassava processor was further randomly selected from each of the processing centres. The Kwara State Agricultural Development Project (ADP)

provided the sampling frame from the list of registered cassava processing centres and groups maintained in the Rural Institutions Development (RID) Department.

A well-structured interview schedule was used as an instrument to elicit information on types and number of processing machines available to processors, gender of operators, source of power and type of prime mover, mode of operation and constraints to mechanization of cassava processing. Kwara state ADP field staffs and Extension Agents (EAs) were trained as research assistants/enumerators, and they assisted in administering the instrument. Focus Group Discussion (FGD) and Key Informant Interview were employed in order to enrich the qualitative data obtained from the groups.

The data collected was analyzed using simple descriptive statistics like mean, percentages and cross tabulations. Chi-square (X^2) analysis was used to test the independence of machine operators against sex (gender). The Chi-square analysis was done using the formula:

$$x^2 = \sum \frac{(F_o - F_e)^2}{F_e}$$

Where;

F_o = the observed frequency

F_e = expected frequency

\sum = summation

X^2 = Chi-square parameter

Through Focus Group Discussion, the major constraints to mechanization of cassava processing were identified. The result was rated on a 4 points Likert-Type scale and ranked to determine their severity.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows the distribution of functional cassava processing machines in the study area. There were about 255 cassava peeling tools, 254 cassava chipping machines, 186 cassava washing basins, 163 cassava frying machines, 120 cassava sieving machines, and 108 cassava pressing machines. Others include about 76 cassava grating machines, 25 cassava milling machines and 14 cassava drying machine. Cassava processing machines such as peelers, washers, and chippers were the most commonly adopted in all the other LGAs. Irepodun LGA had the full range of cassava processing machines listed in this

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study. From the foregoing, it can be concluded that the level of cassava mechanization is highest in Irepodun LGA of Kwara State.

Table 1: Distribution of Functional Cassava Processing Machine.

LGA	Oyun	Ifelodun	Irepodun	Ekiti	Ilorin South	Asa	Total
Peeler	40	34	58	16	41	40	255
Washer	28	25	36	20	29	31	186
Chipper	40	34	58	15	41	40	254
Grater	10	10	10	9	14	14	76
Presser	17	15	10	9	21	18	108
Sifter	4	16	37	-	12	38	120
Fryer	38	22	27	14	18	34	163
Dryer	-	-	14	-	-	-	14
Miller	3	1	10	10	-	1	25

Source: Field Survey, 2015

The power source for cassava processing equipment in the study area and their mode of operation is presented in Table 2. The Table (2) shows that on the average, over 60 percent of the processing equipment are manually powered. Diesel engines powered about 26 percent, while electricity accounted for only 0.5 percent. Table 2 further reveals that 73.5 percent of the machines are manually operated, leaving only 26.3 percent for mechanical operations. Virtually, all peeling, washing, drying, frying and chipping operations are done manually. However, substantial achievements have been recorded in the mechanization of grating and milling operations (90.1% and 87.4% respectively) which are mechanically powered by diesel. This result is in agreement with Igbeka *et al.* (1994) and Adetan *et al.* (2003) who reported that most cassava processing operations are still being done manually. This has great implications, as manual operations are generally labour intensive, arduous in nature, time consuming and unsuitable for large scale production. This result further poses great challenges to research engineers and investors in the downstream sector, including equipment fabricators and the various tiers of government.

Table. 2: Power Source for Equipment & Mode of Operation

Equipment	Power Source				Mode of operation		
	Manual	Diesel	Petrol	Electricity	Manual	Mechanical	Manual/Mechanical
Peeler	100	0	0	0	100	0	0
Washer	100	0	0	0	100	0	0
Chipper	84.5	14.1	1.4	0	85.9	14.1	0
Grater	0	90.1	7	2.8	11.3	87.3	1.4
Presser	1.4	8.5	0	0	63.4	36.6	0
Sifter	59.1	36.6	2.8	1.4	77.5	22.5	0
Fryer	100	0	0	0	100	0	0
Dryer	98.6	1.4	0	0	98.6	1.4	0
Miller	8.5	87.4	4.2	0	24.8	75.2	0
Average	61.3	26.5	1.7	0.5	73.5	26.3	0.2

Source: Field Survey, 2015

*Figures are given in percentage of total equipment sampled.

The distribution of processing equipment as it relates to sex of operator is shown in Table 3. It reveals that cassava peeling, washing, sifting, frying, and drying operations were mostly carried out by the females, while the male folks handled processing machines such as chippers, graters, pressers and millers. The strength required to operate these machines no doubt explains the reasons. However, several cases abound that both males and females operated almost all the machines.

Table 3: Distribution of Equipment by Sex of Operator*

Equipment	Sex of Operator			Total
	Male	Female	Both	
Peeler	2.8	93.0	4.2	100.0
Washer	1.4	94.4	4.2	100.0
Chipper	68.0	25.4	2.8	100.0
Grater	90.1	7.0	2.9	100.0
Presser	84.5	5.6	9.9	100.0
Sifter	26.8	69.0	4.2	100.0
Fryer	9.8	87.4	2.8	100.0
Dryer	2.8	95.8	1.4	100.0
Miller	86.0	14.0	0.0	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2015

*Figures are given in percentage of total equipment sampled.

Table 4 shows the chi-square test for the processing equipment versus the sex of the operator. The analysis in Table 4 revealed that gender (sex) is dependent on processing machine at 1% level of significant. This implies that a sex of an individual could determine to a great extent the machine he or she operates. This confirms the earlier analysis in Table 3, and further agrees with the study of Davies *et al.* (2008), where they reported that females tend to operate cassava processing machines that require lesser energy.

Table 4: Chi-Square Test for Equipment versus Sex of Operator

Equipment	Sex of Operator			
	Male	Female	Both	Total
Peeler	3	112	5	120
Washer	2	113	5	120
Chipper	86	30	4	120
Grater	108	8	4	120
Presser	101	7	12	120
Sifter	32	83	5	120
Fryer	12	105	3	120
Dryer	2	115	3	120
Miller	103	17	0	120
Chi-square	391.486			
p-value	0.001			
Df	8.0			

Table 5: Severity of Constraints to mechanization of Cassava Processing (N=120)

Constraints	4 Very Severe	3 Severe	2 Not Severe	1 Indifferent	Σ	\bar{x}	Rank	Remark
High cost of equipment	45(37.5)	40(33.3)	35(29.2)	5(5.0)	375	3.12	4	Severe
High maintenance Cost	20(16.7)	18(15)	60(50)	22(18.3)	276	2.30	6	Not severe
Poor quality of fabrication materials	14(11.7)	10(8.3)	80(66.7)	16(13.3)	262	2.18	8	Not severe
Scarcity of spare parts	85(70.8)	23(19.2)	10(8.3)	2(1.7)	431	3.59	2	Very severe
Lack of credit facilities	91(75.9)	20(16.7)	8(6.67)	1(8.83)	441	3.68	1	Very severe
Inappropriate processing equipment	10(8.3)	35(29.2)	50(41.7)	25(20.8)	270	2.25	7	Not severe
Lack of electricity/power	69(57.5)	45(37.5)	4(3.3)	2(1.7)	421	3.51	3	Very severe
Ineffective government policy	40(33.3)	30(25.6)	40(33.3)	10(8.3)	340	2.83	5	Severe

Source: Field Survey, 2015.. Parentheses are in percentages

Key: 1.5 – 2.5 =Not severe, 2.6 – 3.5 =Severe, 3.6 and above =Very severe

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Presented in Table 5 is the severity of constraints to mechanization of cassava processing. The 'very severe' constraints are lack of credit, scarcity of spare parts and lack of electricity with respective mean scores of 3.68, 3.59 and 3.51. High cost of equipment and ineffective government policy are considered 'severe' with mean scores of 3.12 and 2.83 respectively; while Poor quality of fabrication materials and Inappropriate processing equipment are considered 'Not severe' with mean scores of 2.25 and 2.18 respectively.

The trend shown in this study is not unexpected, as lack of credit has been identified as a critical factor limiting the ability of processors to access upgraded cassava processing equipment, and hence improve their product quality (UNIDO, 2010). Scarcity of spare parts and poor supply of electricity all combine to increase production costs, making cassava processing economically less attractive.

Conclusion and Recommendations

From the results of this study, it can be concluded that the level of mechanization of cassava processing in Kwara State is generally low. The most commonly available processing equipment were the peeling tool (common knife) which is also used for chipping, the grater and local frying pans. Over 70% of the processing equipment are manually operated, while electricity accounted for only about 0.5%. However, substantial achievements have been recorded in the mechanization of grating and milling operations (90.1% and 87.4% respectively) which are mechanically powered by diesel. Peeling still constitutes the greatest challenge to cassava processing as no processing centre in the entire study area had a mechanical peeler. Operation of the processing equipment are related to the sex of the operator, as the males operated machines that required much energy like the presser, grater and miller. The 'very severe' constraints to mechanization of cassava processing are lack of credit, scarcity of spare parts and lack of electricity, while Poor quality of fabrication materials and Inappropriate processing equipment are considered 'Not severe'.

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made to mitigate the identified constraints to mechanization of cassava processing:

- i) To enhance cassava-processing activities, Government should put in place deliberate fiscal policy to lower interest rate, and reduce complex procedure/stringent conditionality for accessing micro- credit. In this regard, Government should hasten to disburse the 50 billion Naira under the Micro-finance fund at very low interest rate;

- ii) Government should make massive investment in subsidizing cassava processing equipment to encourage diversification of processing options in the downstream sector;
- iii) Cassava processors should be encouraged to form themselves into viable Groups or Association in order to leverage and facilitate access to loans and credit facilities;
- iv) Provision of basic infrastructures like electricity, water, accessible roads and filling stations will not only improve the standard of living of rural processors, but will also help them to adopt machines that use electricity and diesel; and
- v) Adequate funds should be injected into research and development of low-cost but effective cassava processing technologies by agricultural engineers.

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